

Preliminary investigation on anthelmintic activity of crude pine tar against gastrointestinal helminths of goats

Hazrat Bilal¹, Hamayoun Khan¹, Sahib Jan¹, Abdullah², Atta ur Rehman¹, Khurram Ashfaq^{3*},
Anas Abdullah Hamad^{4*}

¹Livestock and Dairy Development Department, Balochistan, Pakistan.

²University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences Lahore, Pakistan.

³Department of Clinical Medicine and Surgery, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad, Pakistan.

⁴Department of Pathological Analysis, College of Applied Science, University of Fallujah, Iraq.

*Corresponding authors: drkhurramashfaq33@gmail.com; dr.anas.a.hamd@uofallujah.edu.iq

Abstract

Parasitism is one of the primary health issues for small ruminants worldwide. Alternative approaches are being explored in response to the growing issue of anthelmintic resistance and herbal medicines stand out as the most crucial due to their effectiveness and accessibility. The present study was designed to investigate the anthelmintic activity of crude extract of pine tar against gastrointestinal helminths of goats. Fecal microscopy of 50 adult goats was carried out, in which positive animals having almost similar eggs per gram were selected, and divided into four groups, namely G1, G2, G3 and G4. G1 and G2 were kept as negative and positive controls, respectively. G1 was served as negative control receiving no medicine/herbal extract while G2 (positive control) was administered with albendazole @ 7.5mg kg⁻¹ body weight. The other two groups namely G3 and G4 were administered with pine tar at dose rate of 5ml and 10ml, respectively. The fecal samples were subjected to the McMaster technique to estimate pretreatment egg per gram (EPG) at day 0 and post treatment EPG at day 7 and 14 of the trial. Trial continued for 30 days and fecal egg count reduction (FECR) at day 7 and 14 of trial was also determined. Mean Egg Per gram (EPG) ±SEM (standard error mean) calculated for group G1, G2, G3 and G4 were recorded at pretreatment (day 0) and post treatment (day7 and 14) respectively. All treatments showed a significant reduction in fecal egg count as compared to control group. fecal egg count reduction of G2, G3 and G4 on day 7 was 54.83%, 8.57% and 16.03% respectively. While on day 14 it was 79.35%, 23.87% and 37.31% respectively. The animals in group G3 and G4 showed significant EPG decline 23.87% and 37.31% respectively at 14th day post treatment as compared to group control untreated (G1). Statistical analysis revealed that G2 was significantly (P<0.05) different at day 0,7 and 14. Subsequently G3 and G4 revealed the same trend/ pattern as G2. The animals in group G2 treated with albendazole showed most significant decline in EPG up to 79.35% at 14th day post-treatment so we conclude that albendazole stood best in this trial as compared to pine tar. However, pine tar can be considered because of growing anthelmintic resistance and toxicity of albendazole. The results of this trial suggested that herbal extract is showing activity against gastrointestinal helminths in goats. The results also show dose and time dependent activity of herbal extract. A crucial component of helminth management in ruminants is reducing pasture contamination, which may be accomplished by FECR up to 37.31% of herbal extract in the current study. Before the tested herbal extract is taken into consideration to investigate its potential as an anthelmintic in the future, standardization of techniques for its extraction, dosing, and large-scale trials are advocated.

Keywords: pine tar; albendazole; anthelmintics; herbal medicine; small ruminants